

Advanced Material Identification in Muon Tomography

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Abstract—Muon tomography employs cosmic ray muons to image the internal structure and material composition of target volumes, such as maritime cargo containers. Despite its potential, the high dimensionality of reconstructed muon tomography data poses challenges for material discrimination and the discernment of structural layouts. In this study, we propose a novel methodology for material identification through the insightful visualization of data embeddings. Our approach synergizes the integrated workflow provided by the Blender-to-Geant4 (B2G4) framework for the rapid simulation of a variety of scenes and the standard muon tomography reconstruction methods. Then, we utilize an unsupervised exploratory data analysis technique along with a novel structured methodology for muon data sampling aimed at discerning materials afforded by the resulting embedding spaces. The experimental results resolve the difficulties in applying machine learning for muon tomography data and highlight new venues for principled material classification.

Index Terms—Muography, Simulations, physics validation, synthetic data

I. INTRODUCTION

Muon scattering tomography (MST) exploits cosmic ray muons to image the internal structure and material composition of concealed areas, referred to as the Volume of Interest (VOI). Figure 1 highlights a generic muon scattering tomography setup, with a VOI containing three objects of different materials. When muons pass through a material, they scatter due to Coulomb interactions with the atomic nuclei within the material [1, 2]. The scattering angle θ can be measured for each pair of muons, and after an exposure time has elapsed, a 3D density map of the VOI can be generated by utilizing a tomographic reconstruction algorithm, for example, Point of Closest Approach (PoCA) [3] or Angle Statistics Reconstruction (ASR) [4]. The common working principle of these algorithms is to retrieve the incoming and outgoing momentum directions in detectors (muon hits), followed by voxelization, where the VOI is segmented into a grid of discrete volumetric elements, or voxels. Then, the scattering angles θ are estimated and assigned as a per-voxel value, the scattering score. The final density maps are produced by aggregating data from all the recorded muons hits to render 3D scattering density maps that reflect the relative densities and spatial arrangement of objects within the VOI. These 3D scattering density maps

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This research was funded by the SilentBorder project under the grant agreement ID 101021812 of the European Union’s Horizon2020 research and innovation program.

Fig. 1. **Visualization of a generic muon scattering setup:** When muons pass through an object (e.g., O_1) in a specific volume of interest (VOI), they undergo scattering as a result of Coulomb interactions with the material’s atomic nuclei. Tomographic algorithms used for muon reconstruction utilize the muon hits to predict the pathways and create a 3D scattering density map.

are the basis of the analysis of non-destructive applications, including security [5], infrastructure monitoring [6], industrial testing [7], or nuclear fuel cask surveillance [8], among others.

Accurate muon momentum measurements are essential for understanding the relationship between scattering angles and material properties. Traditional methods require either strong magnetic fields in short detection volumes or weak fields over large volumes [1], both of which are impractical for most muon tomography applications due to high material costs and construction challenges. Alternative approaches, like inserting intermediate materials between muon detectors to infer momentum from known scattering interactions, suffer from significant uncertainties because single muon scattering has a large random component [2]. Thus, obtaining precise momentum measurements and effectively processing and interpreting muon data, both affected by noise and measurement uncertainties, remain significant obstacles to creating high-quality real-world muon datasets. Additionally, data scarcity poses a significant challenge, limiting the availability of comprehensive datasets required for effective machine learning model training and validation. The development of synthetic data emerges as a promising direction to overcome current muon data scarcity limitations. Typically, muon tomography setups are simulated using Geant4, a sophisticated particle physics simulation software [9]. To this end, Blender-to-Geant4 (B2G4) framework [10] has been proposed to facilitate

Fig. 2. **Datasets generated in this study.** In (a) and (b), the Geant4 imports for the MonkeyContainer and the 4ShapesContainer datasets, respectively. In (c) and (d), the top view of the 3D scattering density maps was retrieved with the PoCA reconstruction algorithm for the MonkeyContainer and the 4ShapesContainer dataset. The container, in white, has a height of 6.0 m, a length of 3.0 m, and a width of 2.4 m. These dimensions correspond to a maritime cargo container.

the rapid prototyping and simulation of detailed 3D scenes for particle physics simulations in Geant4, including muon tomography. B2G4 is a modular data workflow that uses Blender to design 3D scenes for Geant4 simulations, sidestepping the traditionally labor-intensive process of creating 3D scenes for Geant4.

In this work, we demonstrate the effectiveness of the B2G4 framework as a scalable data generator for muon scattering tomography applications, complemented by a structured methodology for data sampling and feature extraction aimed at material identification. To achieve this, we employ a volumetric sampling strategy of the VOI based on pillars, which are widely used in 3D computer vision and autonomous driving [11]. We generate two datasets using B2G4, featuring various geometric shapes and materials ranging from high to low density. We reconstruct the scene using the PoCA approximation from the hits recorded by the ideal detectors, that is, those placed above, below, and on the sides of the VOI. By employing the PoCA approximation, we estimate the incoming and outgoing muon direction vectors necessary for track reconstructions and scattering angles. After reconstructing the scenes and estimating the scattering angles using the standard PoCA reconstruction method, we apply pillar sampling to extract a set of features designed to capture material density variations. We explore various preprocessing techniques to reduce noise in pillar sampling and suggest how convolutions can be used to enhance the PoCA outcome. The extracted pillars are then used as input for a dimensionality reduction technique, t-Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-

SNE) [12], an unsupervised learning approach that creates a simplified representation of the pillars to visualize material distributions. The proposed workflow highlights the challenges that machine learning algorithms face with MST data, suggests improvements, and highlights how these simplified representations effectively distill all material density information into a more interpretable and enriched format suitable for mainstream machine learning tasks, including automatic material classification or density estimation.

II. RELATED WORKS

Simulations in Geant4: Albeit possible, complex scene design in Geant4 is very challenging due to the requirements of manual 3D design, iterative error corrections, compilations, and lack of visualization. To mitigate these problems, the Geometry Description Markup Language (GDML) [13] simplifies the creation of geometries in Geant4 using an XML-based schema, but it requires manual text file manipulation and lacks visual feedback. Alternatives involve converting 3D CAD data or STEP files [14] into GDML or CAD design [15], yet these methods are error-prone with very limited visualization options. An alternative proposed by [16] suggests converting standard 3D files to Geant4 code using the TesselatedFacets feature in Geant4. While this approach simplifies mesh importation into Geant4, it does not support complete 3D scene integration and requires manual coding for geometrical attributes and scene modifications.

Muon data analysis: Machine learning has been explored in MST to analyze muon data from Geant4 simulations [17], with feature discriminators to detect waste drums materials [18], classification of surveyed data [19] or as the core component in muon imaging [20], [21], [22], among others. Despite being state-of-the-art, these approaches do not incorporate large amounts of simulated data; therefore, the generalization of machine learning techniques for complex MST data remains to be explored. An optimization workflow, TomOpt, has been proposed to identify the most effective muon detector setups that meet operational specifications [23]. The TomOpt workflow casts the geometrical configuration of hardware detectors as an end-to-end differentiable procedure designed to find the best set of detector hyper-parameters that fulfill operational specifications.

III. FRAMEWORK DESCRIPTION

This section introduces the use of pillars [11] as a sampling technique in muon tomography data to examine material density distribution within a scanned volume. These pillar structures traverse the reconstructed VOI whilst extracting features, thus allowing the 3D scattering density maps to be divided into manageable segments for further analysis. Then, an unsupervised learning method, t-SNE, is utilized to distill a feature vector representation to visualize and interpret the extracted pillars while facilitating material clustering and identification.

A. Dataset Generation

Figure 2 depicts the two primary datasets generated with the B2G4 framework for material identification in muon tomography. Each dataset contains ten scenes, each scene containing a container with objects made of the chosen materials. The dimensions of this container remain the same for all experiments. In meters, these dimensions are $h_w : 3$ (width), $h_l : 6$ (length), and $z_h : 2.4$ (height), corresponding to those of a maritime cargo container. Given that our interest lies in determining whether material densities can be identified from the reconstruction of 3D scattering density maps, the background composition of the container is initially set as a vacuum. Each scene comprises a set of geometric shapes made from a unique material. These materials are categorized into three groups: high-density materials (Au, Pb, W), medium-density materials (Al, Fe, Cu), and low-density materials (Concrete, Air, Si, Water). We then generate the datasets as follows:

- 1) **MonkeyContainer (Figures 2a, 2c):** We are interested in understanding if different materials can be identified, given a single shape. Hence, this dataset features a container with bare walls and a single monkey head placed at the center. In each scene, the monkey head is made of one material, that being a high, medium, or low-density material. The final dataset contains ten scenes, each with a unique material.
- 2) **4ShapesContainer (Figures 2b, 2d):** This dataset contains different geometrical shapes of the same material. Here, the main focus is to elucidate whether the geometrical shape of objects has an impact on the material identification task. Thus, this dataset contains four primitive shapes, a sphere, a cube, a cylinder, and a monkey head, of smaller sizes, each centered at the center of each quadrant within the container. This is purposely set up to ensure objects at the corners are uniformly radiated. Like the MonkeyContainer dataset, this dataset also has ten scenes.

We run particle simulations after the scenes in each dataset are generated in B2G4 and exported into Geant4. We utilize the Cosmic-ray Shower Library (CRY) [24] to produce particles from cosmic ray air showers from the Z direction downwards. The simulation data is generated by recording only the muon hits, that is, the interaction point between the muon and the detector planes. The specific configuration and characteristics of these sensitive detectors are defined within Geant4. We assume ideal detectors: maximum acceptance no efficient losses, border, or resolution effects are considered.

B. Tomographic Reconstruction

After simulating the scenes from B2G4 with Geant4 using the CRY library, an MST tomography reconstruction algorithm, PoCA, reconstructs each scene for the pillar sampling step. Each scene undergoes reconstruction using the PoCA method with a voxel size of 5.0 cm for both datasets. The selected voxel size suffices for this study, as smaller voxel resolutions would significantly increase computational demands. The

Fig. 3. **Schematic representation of the proposed pillar sampling:** Multiple pillars ($P_{11}, P_{12}, \dots, P_{21}, P_{22}, \dots, P_{nm}$) aligned vertically in the X , Y , and Z axes. Here, n and m represent the total number of grid divisions along the X and Y axes, respectively. We conduct grid sampling across the VOI in the positive X and Y directions, and from each pillar P_{nm} , we extract a 12-dimensional feature vector along the positive $+Z$ direction for analysis.

PoCA algorithm determines the minimal separation between a muon's incident and emergent trajectories to identify a single scattering point [3]. To do so, PoCA uses the positional and directional data of the muon's path before and after deflection to solve the parametric equations of straight lines [3]. Once the scattering point is estimated, the scattering score is assigned to the corresponding voxel. Then, to estimate the scattering angle θ for each voxel, the mean angle of all scatterings that occurred in this voxel is chosen, while angles below 0.01° are filtered out. When the tomographic reconstructions for each dataset is completed, a volumetric array for each scene containing the estimated PoCA points, that is, the 3D scattering density maps, are produced for further analysis.

C. Pillar Sampling in MST

We employ a strategy to extract sparse feature vectors from the 3D scattering density maps for material identification. To achieve this, we use a sampling method inspired by 3D pillars, a method originally intended to discretize the 3D space into vertical columns (pillars) to aggregate and analyze rich multi-scale features for real-time 3D object detection from point clouds in autonomous driving [11], 3D computer vision applications [25] or statistical measures for effective 3D space (or volume) characterization [26]. In the context of pillar sampling, feature vectors are statistical representations derived from each discretized 3D pillar, capturing essential characteristics (features) for 3D volume characterization. We adopt the pillar concept to muon tomography and suggest its modification to the reconstructed tomographic volume, the estimated PoCA. Here, the traditional pillar parameters (sampling grid, range, maximum number of pillars, and maximum

Fig. 4. **t-SNE results with selected pillar samples for interpretation.** (a) t-SNE visualization results of the MonkeyContainer dataset. The numbers represent selected pillar samples for visualization (b) Numbered t-SNE samples for Tungsten (W), Iron (Fe), Aluminium (Al), Concrete, Silicon (Si), Water, and Air. The black lines indicate the position of the pillars in the 3D scene. The pillar position offers discriminative power for the materials. The PoCA assumption and muon energy estimation, showing a diffuse halo around the monkey head due to sampling by the pillars.

number of points per pillar) are conditioned to the tomographic reconstruction. Figure 3 depicts a schematic representation of the proposed pillar sampling strategy. We defined the sampling grid as X , Y , and Z to enclose the boundaries of the container. These boundaries delineate with the VOI, where we will extract the points per pillars, or the features, from reconstructed volume. The sampling step corresponds to one pillar for each position cell in the ideal detector, i.e., for each position ($+X$, $+Y$) in the positive direction of width and height, we compute one pillar positive in-depth, $+Z$ (Figure 3). For each pillar, we derive a set of 12 features designed to capture potential variations in the scattering angles, grouped into two different groups, as follows:

- 1) **Statistical measures:** mean, median, standard deviation, interquartile range, skewness, kurtosis, the maximum and minimum (non-zero) angles of reconstruction. These features offer insight about the pillar density distribution and the materials within.
- 2) **Complexity measures:** energy, normalized entropy, total intensity, and maximum Fourier amplitude [26]. These features offer insights into the energy distribution of the 3D reconstructed scattering density maps.

Our sampling strategy employs vertically oriented pillars that align with the vertical trajectories of the muon path. Since the angle of deflection, θ , is unlikely to result in a horizontal change in position of >5 cm, one pillar is likely to incorporate the entire path of the muon through the volume [3] [5]. Thus, the pillars allow us to assess both the material densities and the potential contribution of the muon paths to the estimated 3D scattering density map. As a result, we can evaluate whether the commonly used PoCA algorithm and its underlying assumptions capture meaningful muon dynamics for mainstream machine learning tasks, including material identification. Given that no deflection occurs on pillars sampled at empty regions, we filter out those from the

analysis.

D. Embedding visualization

In machine learning, an embedding is a very compact, low-dimensional representation of high-dimensional data. We suggest the use of embeddings as an essential tool for understanding reconstructed 3D scattering density maps in MST. The t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) algorithm [12], can be used to visualize the extracted pillars for MST data, as it reduces the distance between high-dimensional data and its lower-dimensional representation. The process starts by calculating pairwise affinities among the data points based on a chosen perplexity value per , which determines the local scale for each data point. Next, the algorithm initializes a low-dimensional representation from a normal distribution and iteratively refines this model. During this optimization process, the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence is used as the primary metric for measuring distance, assessing the difference between two probability distributions. Thus, to derive the embedding vectors, the algorithm minimizes the KL divergence between the joint probability distribution of the data points in the high-dimensional space P and the joint probability distribution from the embeddings in the lower-dimensional space Q :

$$KL[P||Q] = \sum_i \sum_j p_{ij} \log \frac{p_{ij}}{q_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

with P and Q representing the probability distributions in both the high- and low-dimensional spaces, and p_{ij} and q_{ij} denoting the pairwise similarities across data points in these spaces. This minimization process is essential for preserving the topology and information of complex data. The t-SNE algorithm achieves this by projecting representative embeddings into a low-dimensional space, thereby capturing

hidden similarities that are rendered in the low-dimensional space [12].

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Single shape, multiple materials

In this first experiment, we used the MonkeyContainer dataset: a monkey head placed in the center of the container and made of one material: Au, Pb, W, Concrete, Cu, Fe, Air, Al, Si, or Water. For each reconstructed scene, we extract the pillars and run the t-SNE algorithm with the default parameters; the selected perplexity value is $per = 42$ to avoid excessive oversimplification of both, global and local data structures [12].

Material identification: Figure 4 highlights the t-SNE analysis on the extracted pillars for the MonkeyContainer dataset. The black lines shown in Figure 4b refers to regions in the 3D scattering density maps where the pillars are sampled, while the numbers in Figure 4a correspond to those sampled pillars. From Figure 4a, note that low, medium, and high-density materials can be clearly distinguished. This indicates that the 3D scattering density maps reconstructed using the PoCA algorithm can effectively differentiate between various materials if these belong to very distinct densities. For instance, we can notice a separation across high, medium, and low-density materials, as depicted in Figure 4b with W, Fe, Water, and Air. Discrimination across the materials of similar densities proves more challenging, with t-SNE points cluttered across the boundaries of materials whose densities are close, such as Si (2.33 g/cm^3), Al (2.7 g/cm^3) or Concrete (2.4 g/cm^3). The t-SNE analysis shows that the mass of an object could significantly impact machine learning applications. For instance, we can observe that the pillars sampling regions of materials with higher mass yield much more tightly grouped points in the t-SNE analysis, as seen in Fe and Concrete samples (Figure 4b). Further, note that the pillars sampling from reduced mass regions, such as the ears of the concrete monkey, yield a low-dimensional feature vector, similar to pillars sampling from greater mass regions belonging to less dense materials. This effect is inherent to MST since the physical scattering caused by the muon is also dependent on the volume of material present along with the density of the material [2], as seen in Figure 4b for the Al and concrete pillars samples.

Reconstruction bias and muon energy: The PoCA reconstruction algorithm can introduce noise artifacts that impact the sampling strategy, potentially causing bias in machine learning applications. Despite filtering out small angles during reconstruction, these noise artifacts still appear due to the energy spectra of incoming muons and the single-point assumption in PoCA. Figure 4b highlights this effect for Si and Air materials. Incoming muons have a broad energy profile, significantly influencing their penetration and scattering within materials. High-energy muons penetrate deeper and scatter less predictably than lower-energy muons, leading to inconsistencies in the reconstruction algorithm. The PoCA

algorithm accounts for all these energies, resulting in noise estimation in 3D scattering density maps, manifesting as a diffuse halo. When pillars sample these regions, this diffuse halo yields a pillar feature representation that contains much of the background noise. Such effect can further be noticed in all the reconstructions depicted in Figure 4b, yet it is most evident in the tail visible in the tSNE for materials like Silicon or Air, where such noise effects yield pillars intertwined in the low-dimensional space.

B. Multiple shapes, single materials

This experiment focuses on the 4ShapesContainer dataset: four geometrical shapes in the container made of the same material

Proposed corrections: We correct the output of the PoCA algorithm by adjusting for energy-dependent scattering properties. This is done by applying a band-pass filter of muons across the energy band between 2 to 10 GeV. Then, we introduce a 3D convolutional layer that ingests the 3D scattering density maps and produces a denoised, compact representation for pillar sampling. Hence, we define as the lower and upper bounds for the offsets from the center of the kernel ks . The 3D convolutional layer is thus defined as:

$$M(x, y, z) = V(x + i, y + j, z + k) \mid i, j, k \in \left[-\left\lfloor \frac{ks}{2} \right\rfloor, \left\lfloor \frac{ks}{2} \right\rfloor\right] \quad (2)$$

with $V(x + i, y + j, z + k)$ the values in the filtered input 3D scattering density map, with the kernel range (i, j, k) as the displacements within the kernel size, ks centered at the point (x, y, z) . We selected a 3D kernel size of 3 to exploit the spatial relationships between neighbor densities. For each of the denoised representations, we extract the pillars following the sampling procedure detailed in Section III-C, and the t-SNE algorithm with a perplexity value of 42 as detailed in Section III-D. All four geometric shapes are made from the same materials, thus yielding a higher number of pillars in the entire dataset compared to the previous dataset.

Role of 3D convolutions and pillars sampling: Figure 5 highlights the t-SNE results for the newly extracted pillars. The pre-processing step of the 3D scattering maps is showcased in the t-SNE visualization, with a smoother transition from low-density to medium-density to high-density materials, thus aiding in material identification. The proposed 3D convolution considers all the contextual information of neighboring voxels to create the filtered 3D map. This means that the noise introduced in the reconstruction due to the energy related bias of the scattering angle can be corrected by the 3D convolution. As a result, the density is distributed more evenly across the voxels and is not concentrated at just one point. The corrected density map is sampled using pillars, which, being vertical, provide a better approximation for the voxelised 3D scattering density map given that the new features of the pillar are contextual rather than localized. However, this smoothing leads to a more densely packed representation of materials when sampling all the materials in the VOI. When the materials densities

Fig. 5. **Results for the proposed corrections:** (a): t-SNE visualization results for the introduced correction on the 4ShapesContainer dataset. The shape and sampling strategy influences the representation, but incorporating 3D features (convolutions) improves results. (b): 3D reconstructed scattering map with median filter for a water scene.

are close to the background, these can be filtered excessively by the convolution kernels, as the number of Air pillars has greatly diminished, yet these appear grouped in the same region of the t-SNE map. Additionally, the median kernel, if compared with reconstruction results in Figure 4, is observed to preserve edges across these dimensions, thereby aiding in averaging out isolated noise points that do not correlate well with their neighboring material density points.

V. CONCLUSION

Machine learning can enhance muon scattering tomography applications. Yet, data scarcity remains a significant challenge for machine learning, which has led to exploring synthetic data generation as a promising solution. This study proposes a workflow that enhances material identification through the synergistic integration of structured pillar sampling and unsupervised dimensionality reduction techniques. The experimental results highlight that materials of distinct densities can be distinguished, yet the reconstruction bias and muon energy must be considered when building machine learning applications. To address this issue, we propose filtering the muon spectra before the reconstruction of the 3D scattering density maps reconstruction, followed by 3D convolutions to integrate the contextual information from neighboring voxels. The shape and sampling strategy influence the final representation, but incorporating the proposed 3D convolutions greatly improves the outcomes. However, materials with similar densities remain entangled in the t-SNE representation, thus suggesting that material identification would benefit by incorporating

additional physics or by using deep learning architectures that can distill a more powerful feature representation to learn the relationship between scattering angles and a broader range of materials.

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